

Embedding and Evaluating a Pre-Covid-19 MOOC in an Interdisciplinary University Course More Than Five Years Later: E-Tutoring@UIBK and the MekoMOOC, A Case Study

Mag.^a Evelyn Feistmantl¹[0009-0009-4288-0046]

¹ University of Innsbruck, Innrain 52d 6020 Innsbruck, Austria
evelyn.feistmantl@uibk.ac.at

Abstract. This paper aims to illustrate how the course concept for the E-Tutoring@UIBK lecture successfully utilizes the MekoMOOC, a Massive Open Online Course that has been available on the Austrian MOOC platform iMooX since October 1st 2019. More than five years later, the MekoMOOC serves as a vehicle for metacognitive analysis and critical reflection as well as a content pool to introduce students to a variety of media topics. E-Tutoring@UIBK was started with the objective of providing prospective teaching assistants and e-tutors with digital as well as didactic skills and competencies to effectively navigate the digital media landscape of the University of Innsbruck. For this purpose, the course integrates the timeless MOOC contents into its sessions at various points throughout the lecture. The students are tasked to reflect on the structure and didactic purpose of the MOOC's content structure and critically analyze its media composition in order to attain an improved understanding of how to design higher education courses themselves. Finally, the students are asked to produce a tutorial video on a subject matter of their choice. In doing so, students utilize skills and technical knowledge gained through the theoretical and practical aspects of the lecture as well as the MOOC.

Keywords: MOOC-Embedded Learning Design, Experiential MOOC Reuse, MOOC Longevity.

1 Introduction and Methodology

This paper discusses the way that the Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) “#MekoMOOC20: Medienkompetenz in der Lehre” (MekoMOOC) has been integrated into the university lecture E-Tutoring@UIBK in order to showcase a long-term solution for sustainably (re)using MOOCs in teaching endeavors and, thus, guaranteeing their relevancy long-time. The author aims to address in what way E-Tutoring@UIBK is particularly suitable for such an implementation and how this integration may be replicable in other institutions. First, the online course and the lecture series are introduced. MOOC longevity challenges are addressed and the devised link between the MekoMOOC and E-Tutoring@UIBK analyzed in-depth in order to present a case for how

an integration even of older MOOCs into in-person lectures may succeed. Furthermore, the relation between current Artificial Intelligence (AI) developments and MOOC production and trends are discussed. Lastly, the limitations of current AI and OER production endeavors are pointed out and a step-by-step guide for how to integrate a MOOC into a suitable university lecture is provided.

2 The MekoMOOC and E-Tutoring@UIBK

The MekoMOOC is the product of a collaboration between members of several Higher Education Institutions (HEI) and the University of Innsbruck. The first outputs of the project began as two early versions of the MekoMOOC: They started out as modular, supervised online courses (titled #MekoMOOC18 and #MekoMOOC19) that drew a wide audience of 1565 participants (Gröblinger *et al.*, 2019), with 392 certificates issued during their runs. The final version of the MekoMOOC, titled “#MekoMOOC20: Medienkompetenz in der Lehre”, was put online on the Austrian MOOC platform iMooX as a self-paced course on the 1st of October 2019. More than a thousand people have enrolled in it and 289 participants have been issued automated certificates, since (Gröblinger *et al.*, 2019a). The lecture series E-Tutoring@UIBK (Information Technology Services/IT-Center – ZID, 2025), on the other hand, is an in-person course consisting of sessions ranging from media didactics to hands-on trainings for using the technical systems offered at the University of Innsbruck. An elective course creditable for Bachelor students, E-Tutoring@UIBK is open to students of all faculties.

Preservice teacher and e-tutor education thus far has relied commonly on integrating MOOCs with campus-based courses (Edumadze & Govender 2024; Sharma & Singhal 2020; Taguchi *et al.* 2019) in flipped classroom, blended learning or other hybrid learning formats. E-Tutoring@UIBK notably transforms the students’ learning path by putting them in an instructional designer’s role: The students are not simply passive learners but active e-tutors that are tasked to evaluate and analyze the MekoMOOC with a questionnaire before, during and after completing the course (cf. Kember & Leung 2005). Additionally, the MOOC is folded into E-Tutoring@UIBK at various points by way of the topic discussions. As a result, they are engaged in becoming e-tutors, namely teaching assistants with a background on e-learning matters. Their motivation for the completion of the MOOC relies on multiple factors: Their understanding of the reasoning behind going through the course in a pre-determined, question-guided manner and the project of designing and producing a video tutorial on the basis of, among other supplemented materials, the instructional videos in the MekoMOOC.

3 Challenges of MOOC Longevity

From the conception, coordination between the creators from different partner institutions to the creation and the maintenance of a MOOC, its timelessness needs to be factored into the equation (Bou-Vinals *et al.*, 2019; Liu *et al.*, 2019). Having been put online as a self-paced MOOC in 2019, after two runs with active supervision, the course creators needed to design it with continuously evergreen contents in mind: The topics

give a generalized, comprehensive overview on media informatics, media didactics, media law, media usage and the impact of media.

With the fast-changing digital and online landscape in mind, there is a chance that contents may rapidly become outdated. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the institution operating the MOOC (Pomerantz, 2018) to actively commit resources to maintaining it throughout its lifespan. Further academic institutional maintenance of MOOCs is essential because owners of MOOC platforms rarely take up responsibility for doing so. Events such as platform migrations may cause links to the course to break (MiradaX, 2025). The course may also be deleted if no owner actively downloads its contents or agrees to migrating it to a new system. MOOCs offer a static collection of modules and a set curriculum and learning path through the course. This, paired with the lack of personalization options when participants learn in a self-directed manner, may contribute to the high dropout rates: About 69% of MekoMOOC participants show up as “inactive” (Gröblinger, 2019a). Yet, in connection with E-Tutoring@UIBK and the questionnaire, the MekoMOOC was one of the few course requirements that students did not mention as hindering their course success in their session reflections. In general, students self-reportedly underestimating the required total workload seemed to overall be the deciding factor for student dropout from the university course.

4 An Examination of the MekoMOOC and E-Tutoring@UIBK

The MekoMOOC consists of six lessons with an approximate workload of four hours each, with its contents ranging from an introduction about media law to an overview of media didactics. The modules about Open Educational Resources and knowledge management in particular seamlessly complement the contents of the lecture. E-Tutoring@UIBK is a university course being taught by a team of ten different lecturers (ZID, 2025) on the digital tools in use at the University of Innsbruck, didactics and e-assessments at HEI. Generally applicable and quickly evolving subjects, like OER and AI, as well as transferable skills, such as instructions on how to learn to effectively use a learning management system (LMS), are the focus of the in-person sessions. The university course is open to all students at Bachelor level, thus guaranteeing a diverse, heterogenic student pool from different backgrounds and ongoing studies.

E-Tutoring@UIBK as a concept has been transformed multiple times throughout the years (cf. DMLT, 2013; ZID, 2025). By the time of the latest lecture runs, AI applications and use cases have developed exponentially. The MekoMOOC at first glance hosted outdated contents. However, an in-depth perusal of the MOOC proves informative: A comprehensive questionnaire based on existing evaluation frameworks to address the MOOC’s instructional quality (Margaryan *et al.*, 2014; Rice & Ortiz, 2021, cf. Tan, K. H. *et al.*, 2021) was compiled which guides the students through the MOOC in a reflective and purposeful way. Participants are asked to compare and contrast the contents of the MOOC to their knowledge about digital matters and evaluate the MOOC’s instructional quality in detail (cf. Feistmantl & Pinzer-Bakay, 2025).

4.1 The Systematic Deconstruction of the MekoMOOC

The question catalogue for the MekoMOOC is provided to them in the E-Tutoring@UIBK course on the university's LMS. Questions can be asked in a supervised forum of this simultaneously maintained online course. Unlike other tasks, the question catalogue so far has featured the least in students' frequently asked questions for this course, indicating the clarity and straightforwardness of the answers required within.

The questions needed to be answerable solely by going through the MekoMOOC in a structured manner. Question generation followed a systematic deconstruction process based on proven learning and knowledge acquisition theories and strategies, e.g., mind maps as perpetuated as learning vehicles by Tony Buzan (Buzan, 2005), spacing, interleaving, retrieval practice and elaboration (Madan, 2023; Brown *et al.*, 2014), and established question techniques (Krosnick, 2018; Booth, 2006).

First, students are asked questions on the MekoMOOC's structure, about their expectations and ideas for creating a MOOC, themselves. Considerations at the beginning of as well as the motivations for designing a MOOC are addressed (cf. Sanchez-Gordon & Luján-Mora, 2017; Najafi *et al.*, 2017; Najafi *et al.*, 2015; Lopes *et al.*, 2015). The students' critical thinking is facilitated further by way of asking them for suggestions for preventatively handling future (digital) challenges. They are encouraged to proactively seek to meet future expenditures while in the creation phase of a MOOC, a transferable experience they can then go on to use for prospective online teaching endeavors. A retrospective questionnaire allows students to analyze the project in its entirety: from the MOOC project's starting point to its usage to the participants profiting from the contents post-project (and post-funding) (cf. Rodriguez & Rodriguez Nieto, 2019).

After these preliminary questions, the students are tasked to rate the structure of the lessons in the MekoMOOC along with more general questions about the lessons themselves: Each lesson is deconstructed, with students answering questions about the supplementary material and about the usefulness of the MekoMOOC's contents in the context of their diverse backgrounds and study areas, their personal experiences and (future) work aspirations. In addition to these, detailed questions about the videos steer the students' attention towards more practical, technical aspects that tie back to the lecture and are important for their own production of a video tutorial. As a result, they become active agents of their own learning (Little, 2003).

Upon MOOC completion, the students are asked if they missed any information and what topics they would have liked to study more in-depth. For the latter they are given literature and course recommendations (cf. DMLT, 2025; DMLT, 2025a), which some have then gone on to work through independently. These questions take the students into the mindset of a teacher and prompt them to analyze their learning journey in depth.

The question catalogue is a powerful tool for furthering the students' understanding and their competence for analyzing an online course. This reflective activity (RA) (Arañeta *et al.*, 2024) combined with the university lecture allows them to obtain a comprehensive learning experience guiding them gradually into the role of an e-tutor or TA.

4.2 Linking the MOOC with the University Lecture

Teaching with the help of a MOOC in a higher education context is, to this day, a rare phenomenon (de Lima Guedes *et al.*, 2022; Ferri, P. 2019; Jansen *et al.*, 2015). The preparation of the MOOC, the implementation of the way that one would instruct and motivate the students to use it as well as what contents from the MOOC are included in the course material need to be selected carefully. The learning objectives as well as the course assessment have to be considered – a MOOC may supplement contents, however the main objective is to create a learning experience for the students that allows them to retain information as well as analyze and evaluate the teachings, themselves. As such, a MOOC may for example be added to a course’s in-person sessions in a blended learning course format – the most common format for embedding a MOOC in a lecture series (Alario-Hoyos *et al.* 2023; de Lima Guedes *et al.* 2022; Israel, M.J. 2015). Nonetheless, E-Tutoring@UIBK selected to go a slightly different route: The MekoMOOC is used alongside the course, the only requisite for finishing it being a deadline for handing in the MOOC’s completion certificate close to the last session of the lecture.

Within the first on-campus session, students are led through a tutorial on how to create the tutorial video that they have to complete in order to successfully finish the lecture: They are shown the studios that the University of Innsbruck offers them as well as various methods for creating a video. The students have to apply the same time management skills and discipline for successfully completing the MekoMOOC as they do for a mandatory video production self-learning course, reinforcing the need for effective self-management and self-motivation. On top of that, the videos of the MekoMOOC model to the students how to transfer knowledge effectively.

The interwovenness of the MOOC and lecture contents, especially in later sessions, guarantee an effective learning experience with structured interleaved learning periods, spaced retrieval practices and elaboration of obtained knowledge about theories and practical applications thereof (cf. Brown *et al.*, 2014): The in-person session about OER, CC-licenses as well as accessibility for example complement the information covered in Lesson 4 and 6 of the MekoMOOC: Practical use cases for OER usage (Muuß-Merholz, 2018) supplement the lecture, wherein student knowledge from the MekoMOOC is used for discussions about copyright restrictions, digital accessibility issues and OER. The students learn that the knowledge obtained from the MOOC can be applied and discussed in a reflective manner (Araneta *et al.* 2024), even if not all of them have finished the referenced modules. On the other hand, the lecture sessions on knowledge management and data protection remain largely independent from the MOOC, although the topics are touched upon in Lesson 6, too.

Meaningful learning can happen when students understand the usefulness and practical implementation of the material (Brown *et al.*, 2014). Rote memorization is helpful in contexts that are situated at a lower level in Bloom’s taxonomy, whereas the reflective understanding and application of knowledge is encouraged by the active examination of the MOOC. The questions train them to contest and reflect on how they are taught, how they retain information and how they might then go about teaching others about their expertise (Araneta *et al.*, 2024). Autonomous learning, not to be misunderstood as self-instructed learning (Little, 2000, 2007; Hamidullayeva & Fayziqulovna,

2023), which has so far mainly been studied in language learning contexts, is proposed to play a crucial role in future academic course design.

The intention behind utilizing the MOOC to further students' learning is to help them improve their time management, discipline as well as accompany them on the first steps towards an autodidactic learning journey. Their self-efficacy in going through the MOOC ties into their ability to contribute to discussions in in-person sessions, which has proven to enhance learning success (Saliha, Samia 2024). The focus in this kind of interweaving of contents on participatory learning designs (Casanova *et al.*, 2020) and a project-based learning approach gives students the necessary skills to obtain digital competencies and media literacy necessary for future work and study endeavors.

5 Discussion: (Re-)Using MOOCs in times of AI

With the rise of AI and the ever-changing digital landscape, MOOCs form a background well of knowledge and information that one can draw from to support one's teaching. Concerns, such as the fair assessment of students' competencies, or their "AI-supported competency simulations" (Krommer, 2025) largely fall to the wayside for an elective course that has the production of a tutorial video as one of the main assessment criteria and learning objectives. Generative AI and diffusion model development have come far, but the production of videos with AI may need many more improvements before it is at a level to reliably produce output comparable to that of a student's tutorial video. Students' knowledge about AI matters and their competency at using AI is another aspect that should neither be over- nor underestimated (cf. Tulis *et al.*, 2024).

Due to the age of the MekoMOOC showing, this course could not simply be included in the E-Tutoring@UIBK lecture without preliminary considerations on the part of the course lecturers, in particular regarding possible AI implementations and the tasks required for the lecture. The question catalogue that accompanies the students on their learning journey through the MekoMOOC was devised with experiential reflections in mind. Successfully concluding the MOOC and handing in the answers to this question catalogue is one of the five main tasks students have to accomplish throughout the lecture: Regular reflections on the in-person sessions, their presence and active participation in class, the completion of a self-learning course on video production, a final presentation and the production of a tutorial video on a topic of their choice add up to a total of 5 ECTS that students stand to gain upon finishing the lecture. Few of these tasks lend themselves to a substitution through AI applications. Students are made aware of possible repercussions on their knowledge retention, performance in class and limitations of AI throughout the lecture. This preventative measure requires for course lecturers to be aware of the current developments of AI to the best of their abilities.

In times when MOOCs themselves can be created with the use of AI (e.g. Ebner & Schön, 2024), the facilitation for students to use AI applications as tools rather than all-knowing entities must be improved upon. For this to work, the schooling of teaching personnel on the limitations and opportunities of AI is vital. On the other hand, the conception and production of OER might stand to gain much in the utilization of AI as a tool (e.g., as a sounding board for the creation of ideas). With DeepSeek as an Open-Source publication, the collaboration in the global community may soon bring forth

new models with improved and more sustainable backgrounds than those that exist now (cf. Verma & Tan, 2024). Future AI models might be able to integrate with LMS or they may provide a new way to aid the students in retaining knowledge: AI tutors already exist, however they offer limited functions as of yet.

6 Limitations

Keeping in mind the current limitations of AI and the project-based approach of the E-Tutoring lecture, the existing variety of applications for a MOOC in a lecture may prove insufficient for guiding the students towards their goal. New modes for using MOOCs in educational contexts are needed to integrate the online courses into innovative teaching contexts at HEIs. Additionally, the reuse of MOOCs from an instructor's perspective has thus far not been studied sufficiently in depth: Case studies and qualitative literary reviews promise a good starting point. Nonetheless, more quantitatively oriented research may prove informative for how many MOOCs have been used in what way at what level of education. A preliminary method for making the usage of MOOCs at HEIs more visible is by way of MOOC fellowships on iMooX (iMooX, 2025).

Furthermore, MOOC dropout rates once a supervised course has transitioned into a self-paced format are empirically known to rise drastically; dropout rates of elective courses which utilize MOOCs have not yet been studied in-depth. For E-Tutoring@UIBK, dropout risks are largely mitigated by the fact that students take up an active role to identify themselves with (e-tutor) and the meaningful engagement with the material together with other students from an interdisciplinary background.

7 Conclusion

The unique point of departure for the conception of the E-Tutoring@UIBK university course as a formation for prospective e-tutors allows for a modified approach to the utilization of the MekoMOOC: Instead of “only” having the students complete the MOOC, they are to actively engage with the instruction practice by evaluating and assessing the MOOC's contents and instruction delivery, themselves. This reflective approach may not work in less project oriented educational contexts, however, it may be perfectly suited for teacher educational programs. In these settings, the MOOC integration can be replicated with the following steps:

1. A MOOC suitable for such an integration needs to be researched (an introductory MOOC to media competencies for teaching professionals is ideal),
2. A question catalogue regarding the MOOC has to be designed (the question catalogue as referenced in this paper has been published as an OER by Feistmantl & Pinzer-Bakay)
3. The questionnaire needs to be posed to the students
4. Several of the topics discussed in the MOOC need to be embedded in an accompanying lecture (through discussions of case studies and other methods)

The systematic deconstruction of the MekoMOOC is in ongoing development, with these questions forming a foundation for integrating it in future runs of the E-

Tutoring@UIBK lecture. In 2010, MOOCs have been lauded as disruptive for the future of education at HEI (Haug *et al.* 2024). With a similar hype around AI applications nowadays, implications for MOOC creation and maintenance – in particular, MOOC ownership and OER licensing – cannot be specified as of yet.

Disclosure of Interests. The author has no competing interests to declare.

References

1. Alario-Hoyos, C., Delgado Kloos, C., Kiendl, D., Terzieva, L.: Innovat MOOC: Teacher Training on Educational Innovation in Higher Education. Meinel. In: C., Schweiger, S., Staubitz, T., Conrad, R., Alario-Hoyos, C., Ebner, M., Sancassani, S., Zur, A., Friedl, C., Halawa, S. A., Gamage, D., Cross, J. S., Jonson Carlon, M. K., Deville, Y., Gaebel, M., Delgado Kloos, C., von Schmieden, K. (eds.) *Post-Covid Prospects for Massive Open Online Courses: 8th European MOOCs Stakeholders Summit, EMOOCs 2023*, (Potsdam, Germany, 14th-16th June 2023). 229-237, Potsdam: Universitätsverlag Potsdam. (2023)
2. Aldahdouh, A. & Osório, A.: Planning To Design MOOC? Think First! *The Online Journal of Distance Education and e-Learning*. 4(2). 47-57. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.48804>. (2016)
3. Araneta, M. G., Liotino, M., Olatunji, T. I., Fedeli, M.: Leveraging massive open online courses to foster reflective practice in blended university courses. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*. 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2024.2320697>. (2024)
4. Booth, A.: Clear and present questions: Formulating questions for evidence based practice. *LIBRARY HI TECH*. 24(3). 355-368. <https://doi.org/10.1108/07378830610692127>. (2006)
5. Bou-Vinals, A.: #MekoMOOC18: Medienkompetenz in der Lehre. Lernziele. *Universität Innsbruck*. (2018) https://www.uibk.ac.at/projects/mekomoooc/lernziele_meko-mooc.html (last accessed 05.03.2025)
6. Bou-Vinals, A., Brigo, A., Hoffmann, B.: Workshop: Wie erstelle ich einen MOOC?. 5. Österreichische Citizen Science Konferenz (Oberurgl, Austria, 26th-28th June 2019). (2019)
7. Brown, P. C., Roediger, H. L. III, & McDaniel, M. A.: *Make it stick: The science of successful learning*. Cambridge (USA), London: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press. pp. 207. (2014)
8. Buzan, T.: *The ultimate book of mind maps: unlock your creativity, boost your memory, change your life*. London: HarperCollinsPublishers Limited. (2005)
9. Casanova, D., Huet, I., Garcia, F., Pessoa, T.: Role of technology in the design of learning environments. *Learning Environments Research*. 23. 413-427. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10984-020-09314-1> (2020)
10. de Lima Guedes K. K., Davis H. C., & Schulz J.: Integrating MOOCs into traditional higher education modules: a MOOC-based blend framework. *Research in Learning Technology*. 30. <https://doi.org/10.25304/rlt.v30.2702> (2022)
11. Digital Media and Learning Technologies – DMLT: 179001 E-Learning Anwender Grundlagen und eTutorInnenausbildung. *Universität Innsbruck*. (2013) https://lfuonline.uibk.ac.at/public/lfuonline_lv.de-tails?sem_id_in=13W&lvnr_id_in=179001 (last accessed 06.03.2025)
12. DMLT: Crashkurs E-Didaktik. *OpenCourses, Universität Innsbruck*. (2025) <https://open-courses.uibk.ac.at/auth/RepositoryEntry/2981904/CourseNode/99925983867696> (last accessed 30.04.2025)

13. DMLT: OER-Zertifizierungskurs. *OpenCourses, Universität Innsbruck*. (2025a) <https://opencourses.uibk.ac.at/auth/RepositoryEntry/12058624/Course-Node/109846075778424> (last accessed 30.04.2025)
14. Ebner, M., Schön, S.: Open Educational Resources (OER) in Higher Education. *iMooX*. (2024) <https://imoox.at/course/OERinHE> (last accessed 06.03.2025)
15. Feistmantl, E., Pinzer-Bakay, F.: Reflexionsfragen zum MekoMOOC. *Universität Innsbruck*. (2025) <https://oer-repo.uibk.ac.at/edu-sharing/components/render/830d019d-dd86-44ee-8d01-9ddd8614ee43> (last accessed 30.04.2025)
16. Ferri, P.: MOOC, didattica universitaria digitale e Learning analytics. Opportunità e prospettive. *GIORNALE ITALIANO DELLA RICERCA EDUCATIVA, Numero Speciale* (Settembre 2019). 13-26. (2019)
17. Fowler, F. J.: Designing questions to be good measures. In: *Designing questions to be good measures* (4th ed.) 86-113. SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452230184.n6> (2009)
18. Fundación Telefónica: Miriada X. (2025) <https://www.miriadax.net> – This website has not been reachable between 14.02.2025 and 17.04.2025.
19. Gordon, S., Luján, S.: Proceso de desarrollo y gestión de MOOC. *Ciencia América*. 6(2). 162-167. (2017)
20. Gráinne C.: Designing effective MOOCs. *Educational Media International*. 52(4). 239-252. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09523987.2015.1125989> (2015)
21. Gröblinger, O., Bou-Vinals, A., Hoffmann, B., Komar, J. L., Brigo, A.: “MOOCs in Citizen Science”. *Proceedings of EMOOCs 2019: Work in Progress Papers of the Research, Experience and Business Tracks*. EMOOCs 2019 (Naples, Italy, 20th-22th May 2019). p. 137. (2019).
22. Gröblinger, O., Ebner, M., Schedler, M., Schroffenegger, T., Schmid, S., Brandhofer, G., Miesenberger, K., Höfler, E.: #MekoMOOC20: Medienkompetenz in der Lehre. *iMooX*. (2019a) <https://imoox.at/course/mekomoooc2020> Course statistics accessed on 05.03.2025.
23. Hamidullayeva, K. Z., Fayziqulovna, M. Z.: Project-Based Learning as an Effective Teaching Approach to Promote Learner Autonomy. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*. 2(3). 255-258. (2023)
24. Haug, N., Dan, S., Mergel, I.: Digitally-induced change in the public sector: a systematic review and research agenda. *Public Management Review*. 26(7). 1963-1987. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2023.2234917> (2024)
25. iMooX: MOOC Fellowships. (2025) <https://imoox.at/page/fellowship> (last accessed 06.03.2025)
26. Information Technology Services (IT-Center) – ZID: E-Tutoring@UIBK. *Universität Innsbruck*. (2025) <https://www.uibk.ac.at/zid/servicekatalog/servicebeschreibungen/e-tutoring-at-uibk.html> (last accessed 05.03.2025).
27. Israel, M. J.: Effectiveness of Integrating MOOCs in Traditional Classrooms for Undergraduate Students. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*. 16. 102-118. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v16i5.2222> (2015)
28. Jansen, D., Schuwer, R., Teixeira, A. & Aydin, C.: Comparing MOOC Adoption Strategies in Europe: Results from the HOME Project Survey. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*. 16(6). 116–136. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v16i6.2154> (2015)
29. Kember, D., Leung, D.: The Influence of Active Learning Experiences on the Development of Graduate Capabilities. *Studies in Higher Education*. 30. 155-170. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070500043127> (2005)

30. Krommer, A.: “KI-gestützte Kompetenz-Simulation“ (2025) <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7273459084895383552/> (last accessed 07.03.2025)
31. Krosnick, J. A.: Improving Question Design to Maximize Reliability and Validity. In: D. Vannette, & J. Krosnick (eds.), *The Palgrave Handbook of Survey Research*. 95-101. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-54395-6_13 (2018)
32. Liu, M., Zha, S., He, W.: Digital Transformation Challenges: A Case Study Regarding the MOOC Development and Operations at Higher Education Institutions in China. *TechTrends*. 63. 621–630. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-019-00409-y> (2019)
33. Little, D.: Learner autonomy and second/foreign language learning. In: *The Guide to Good Practice for Learning and Teaching in Languages, Linguistics and Area Studies* (2003) <https://web-archive.southampton.ac.uk/www.llas.ac.uk/resources/gpg/1409.html> (last accessed 06.03.2025)
35. Lopes, A. P., Soares, F., Vieira, I.: How to feel “in love” with a math – a MOOC experience. *Proceedings of INTED2015 Conference*. (Madrid, Spain, 2nd-4th March 2015). 326-332. (2015)
36. Madan, C.: Using Evidence-Based Learning Strategies to Improve Medical Education. *Medical Science Educator*. 33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40670-023-01798-9> (2023)
37. Muuß-Merholz, J.: *Freie Unterrichtsmaterialien finden, rechtssicher einsetzen, selbst machen und teilen*. (1st ed.), Verlagsgruppe Beltz, Weinheim Basel. pp. 26 & pp. 133. (2018)
38. Najafi, H., Rolheiser, C., Harrison, L., Håklev, S.: University of Toronto Instructors’ Experiences with Developing MOOCs. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*. 16(3). 233–255. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v16i3.2073> (2015)
39. Najafi, H., Rolheiser, C., Håklev, S., Harrison, L.: Variations in pedagogical design of massive open online courses (MOOCs) across disciplines. *Teaching & Learning Inquiry*. 5(2). <http://dx.doi.org/10.20343/teachlearninqu.5.2.5> (2017)
40. Padilla Rodriguez, B.C., Rodriguez Nieto, M.C.: How to Run a Massive Open Online Course Once the Funding is Over. In: Calise, M., Delgado Kloos, C., Reich, J., Ruiperez-Valiente, J., Wirsing, M. (eds) *Digital Education: At the MOOC Crossroads Where the Interests of Academia and Business Converge. EMOOCs 2019. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 11475. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-19875-6_18 (2019)
41. Pritchett, N.: Effective Question Design. In: Brown S., Bull J. and Race P (eds.) *Computer-Assisted Assessment in Higher Education*. London: Kogan Page Ltd. (1999)
42. Rice, M. F., & Ortiz, K. R.: Evaluating Digital Instructional Materials for K-12 Online and Blended Learning. *TechTrends for leaders in education & training*. 65(6). 977–992. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-021-00671-z> (2021)
43. Tan, K.H.; Chan, P.P.; Mohd Said, N.-E. Higher Education Students’ Online Instruction Perceptions: A Quality Virtual Learning Environment. *Sustainability*. 13(19). 10840. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910840> (2021)
44. Tulis, M., Kinskofer, F., Fischer, E.: ERGEBNISSE DER QUANTITATIVEN ERHEBUNG ZUR KI-NUTZUNG AN HOCHSCHULEN. In: Brandhofer, G., Gröbinger, O., Jadin, T., Raunig, M., Schindler, J. (eds.). *Von KI lernen, mit KI lehren: Die Zukunft der Hochschulbildung. Projektbericht*. 74-123. (2024)
45. Verma, P., Tan, S.: A bottle of water per email: the hidden environmental costs of using AI chatbots. (2024) <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/2024/09/18/energy-ai-use-electricity-water-data-centers/> (last accessed 07.03.2025)
46. Vizerektorat für Digitalisierung und Nachhaltigkeit: 110001 VU E-Tutoring@UIBK. *Universität Innsbruck*. (2025) https://lfuonline.uibk.ac.at/public/lfuonline_lv-details?sem_id_in=24W&lvnr_id_in=110001 (last accessed 05.03.2025)